

USING DIFFERENT WAYS TO ENHANCE ORAL SPEECH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6466922>

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Annotation: *This thesis includes some information about importance of speaking, and some information is given about the role of watching videos, movies, talks and listening to songs, fairy tales in English in forming productive skills, the using of them during the lesson.*

Key words: *education, learning, speaking, listening, talks, songs, imitation, videos, films, organizational learning, special education, classroom management.*

Speaking is one of the important skills that there are some difficulties to form that skill for new learners naturally. Why should we teach speaking skills in the classroom?

In today's modern world, learning spoken English has many advantages. English is fast becoming the international language of many fields, including politics, business and education. Not only is English used between native speakers and non-native speakers, but it is also used increasingly as a common language in interactions between non-native speakers. Listen to the radio, you could get up five minutes earlier and listen to the news in English. Try watching the news in English instead of Uzbek. If you watch a movie and it has subtitles, try taping a paper over them. Invite your English teacher to lunch! Find a friend who also wants to improve his or her English and have lunch or dinner together to speak English of course. Check out books, records, cassette tapes, and other materials in English from your local library. Look especially for books which have lots of dialogue in them. Read plays when you go to see English films, try not to read the Uzbek subtitles. Watch for notices of English activities and join in whenever you can. Seek out lectures in English on topics of interest to you. Try to take notes just for your own use. Find books-on-tape in your local library. Listen while you are relaxing at home or while commuting if you have a walkman. Watch for plays or dramatic performances given in English on campus or get the student ticket for the public performances. Exchange taped messages with a classmate. Record a few minutes and then ask your classmate to respond later on the same tape. Choose a famous

person whose accent you admire, and if you can get recordings of him or her, imitate the way he or she speaks. Practice situations when you are alone, perhaps in front of a mirror. Imagine introducing yourself, disagreeing with someone's ideas, being interviewed or asking for information. If you can get someone to help, assign parts and do role-playing. Make friends with the exchange students on our campus—they are here because they want cross-cultural communication. Communicate with them. Take part in a play in English start out with a small part if you feel shy. Find a friend or two and agree to speak English at certain regular times after a class together, at dinner every Tuesday, or riding home on the train. Practice reading aloud gets someone to check your pronunciation and intonation, or record yourself on tape and analyze your own speech. Set goals of specific things you can work on improving for example, differences between words that contain "l" and "n" or "w" and "v". Keep notes of words you often mispronounce and practice them. If you have a chance to travel, take advantage of the opportunities to use English airlines and immigration personnel, hotel and restaurant staff, fellow travelers and passengers. Visit a former English teacher either from secondary school or from a course you took at university. Teachers like to hear how their students are doing. Everyone knows that the only really effective way to improve on language skills is to use the language. In reality, however, we know that there are many reasons why people don't want to speak in another language they are afraid of making mistakes, they can't express their real meaning easily, they are shy, they are afraid people will laugh at them.

A completely different reason for student silence may simply be that the class activities are boring or are pitched at the wrong level. Very often our interesting communicative speaking activities are not quite as interesting or as communicative as we think they are and all the students are really required to do is answer 'yes' or 'no' which they do quickly and then just sit in silence or worse talking noisily in their L1. So maybe you need to take a closer look at the type of speaking activities you are using and see if they really capture student interest and create a real need for communication.

Another way to encourage your students to speak in English is simply to speak in English yourself as much as possible in class. If you are shy about speaking in English, how can you expect your students to overcome their fears about speaking English? Don't worry if you are not completely fluent or don't have that elusive perfect native accent, as Swain (1985) wrote "We learn to speak by speaking" and that goes for teachers as well as students. The more you practise the

more you will improve your own oral skills as well as help your students improve theirs.

If students do not have something to say or do, or don't feel the need to speak, you can be sure it won't be long before they are chatting away in their L1.

Many students equate being able to speak a language as knowing the language and therefore view learning the language as learning how to speak the language, or as Nunan (1991) wrote, "success is measured in terms of the ability to carry out a conversation in the (target) language." Therefore, if students do not learn how to speak or do not get any opportunity to speak in the language classroom they may soon get de-motivated and lose interest in learning. On the other hand, if the right activities are taught in the right way, speaking in class can be a lot of fun, raising general learner motivation and making the English language classroom a fun and dynamic place to be.

Speaking is fundamental to human communication

Just think of all the different conversations you have in one day and compare that with how much written communication you do in one day. Which do you do more of? In our daily lives most of us speak more than we write, yet many English teachers still spend the majority of class time on reading and writing practice almost ignoring speaking and listening skills. Do you think this is a good balance? If the goal of your language course is truly to enable your students to communicate in English, then speaking skills should be taught and practised in the language classroom. Dealing with common arguments against teaching speaking skills in the classroom students won't talk or say anything

One way to tackle this problem is to find the root of the problem and start from there. If the problem is cultural, that is in your culture it is unusual for students to talk out loud in class, or if students feel really shy about talking in front of other students then one way to go about breaking this cultural barrier is to create and establish your own classroom culture where speaking out loud in English is the norm. One way to do this is to distinguish your classroom from other classrooms in your school by arranging the classroom desks differently, in groups instead of lines or by decorating the walls in English language and culture posters. From day one teach your students classroom language and keep on teaching it and encourage your students to ask for things and to ask questions in English. Giving positive feedback also helps to encourage and relax shy students to speak more. Another way to get students motivated to speak more is to allocate a percentage of their final grade to speaking skills and let the students know they are being assessed continually on their speaking practice in class throughout the term.

We need more time to improve our spoken English and we should practice more. Spoken English plays an important role in English learning. And a good level of communicative competence is the final aim of English learning. How to cultivate and improve the learners' competence of spoken English has become the focal point. By using these methods, the learner can achieve his ideal goals.

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